

10 Research findings about nature-based enterprises

Based on 113 validated responses from nature-based enterprises in 22 countries (86% from Europe, 14% rest of the world) to Connecting Nature survey conducted from January to March 2020.

Nature-based enterprises (NBEs) use nature as a core element of their product/service offering.

Nature may be used directly by growing, harnessing, harvesting or restoring natural resources in a sustainable way and/or indirectly by contributing to the planning, delivery or stewardship of sustainable nature-based solutions.

1 Nature-based enterprises are highly varied in nature. Survey responses came from nature conservation NGOs, community-garden enterprises, 'living wall' suppliers, tech start-ups using satellite data to monitor the quality of urban nature and many more.

2 Nature-based enterprises (NBEs) are increasing year on year

NBE turnover

The private sector is almost as important as the public sector as a source of turnover

8 Twice as many NBEs believe they will be impacted negatively rather than positively by Covid-19

Economic value created:

Environmental value created:

Social value created:

The majority of nature-based enterprises operate at local, regional or national level